

**Notes on some rare flea beetles of the Carpathian Basin
(Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae)**

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Abstract – Distributional and ecological data on some rare flea beetles (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae: Alticitae) of the Carpathian Basin are provided. *Longitarsus albineus* (Foudras, 1860) is reported for the first time from Serbia, *Epitrix hirtipennis* (Melsheimer, 1847) for the first time from Serbia and Romania. New localities and comments on rare flea beetles from Hungary are also given.

Key words – Galerucinae, Alticitae, *Epitrix*, *Longitarsus*, new records, faunistics, literature, host plants

INTRODUCTION

The flea beetle fauna (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae: Alticitae) of the Carpathian Basin is well-studied. The last comprehensive account for the Carpathian Basin as a whole and for Hungary in particular was published by VIG (2003). Subsequent additions and deletions to the checklist of Hungary were made by VIG (2009), BODOR (2010), MERKL *et al.* (2010, 2012), FRITZLAR (2021), LUKÁTSI *et al.* (2022), and TAMÁSI *et al.* (2025). MAICAN (2005) published a checklist of the species known from Romania. Species occurring in Serbia were listed by GAVRILOVIĆ & ČURČIĆ (2011) and further additions were published by GAVRILOVIĆ & ČURČIĆ (2013).

Recent field collections by the first author have confirmed the presence of *Longitarsus albineus* (Foudras, 1860) in Serbia and that of *Epitrix hirtipennis* (Melsheimer, 1847) in Serbia and Romania. Additionally, new records of several rare flea beetle species are reported from Hungary.

The studied specimens are housed in the Coleoptera Collection of the Hungarian National Museum Public Collection Centre – Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest, Hungary (HNHM), and in the private collections

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of the authors, namely in the collection of Márk Lukátsi, Budapest, Hungary (CLM), and in the collection of Laura Farina, Casatenovo, Lecco, Italy (CFL). Specimens with dissected genitalia are marked with “!”. The sex of the specimens is indicated only if it could be determined unambiguously, either through examination of the genitalia or distinct secondary sexual characters.

RESULTS

Epitrix hirtipennis (Melsheimer, 1847)

Material examined – **Hungary:** Bács-Kiskun County, Kiskunfélegyháza, Belső-Galambos, fallow, 46.7050°N, 19.8026°E, from *Datura stramonium* L. (Solanaceae), 22.IX.2024, leg. M. Lukátsi & V. A. Nagy, det. M. Lukátsi (1 CLM); Csongrád-Csanád County, Szeged, Kisteleki út, maize stubble-field, 46.2964°N, 20.0810°E, from *Datura stramonium*, 22.IX.2024, leg. M. Lukátsi & V. A. Nagy, det. M. Lukátsi (1 CLM); Fejér County, Csákvár, Papföldek, 28.IX.2024, from *Datura stramonium*, leg. & det. M. Lukátsi (3 CLM, 3 (1 male!, 1 female!) HNHM); Jász-Nagykun-Szolnok County, 8 km S of Karcag, 47.2429°N, 20.9555°E, from *Datura stramonium*, 1.IX.2024, leg. & det. M. Lukátsi (2 CLM, 2 HNHM); Jász-Nagykun-Szolnok County, Szajol, Alamand-dűlő, 47.1661°N, 20.2672°E, from *Datura stramonium*, 1.IX.2024, leg. & det. M. Lukátsi (2 CLM); Pest County, Cegléd, Öregszőlő, stubble-field, 47.2160°N, 19.7356°E, from *Datura stramonium*, 1.IX.2024, leg. & det. M. Lukátsi (3 CLM, 3 HNHM). **Romania:** Bihar County, Leş, sunflower field, 46.9820°N, 21.8631°E, from *Datura stramonium*, 1.IX.2024, leg. & det. M. Lukátsi (1 CLM, 1 female! HNHM). **Serbia:** Voivodina Region, Stari Žednik, stubble-field, 46.0003°N, 19.6491°E, from *Datura stramonium*, 22.IX.2024, leg. M. Lukátsi & V. A. Nagy, det. M. Lukátsi (1 HNHM).

Distribution – Native to North and Central America. Widely distributed in the contiguous United States wherever tobacco is grown (EDDE 2022); it also occurs in the Bahamas, Canada, Cuba, Mexico, Panama, Puerto Rico in the Americas, Tahiti, Fiji and Hawaii in the Pacific, and Sri Lanka, the Philippines, Syria, and Turkey in Asia (BIEŃKOWSKI & ORLOVA-BIENKOWSKAJA 2016).

In Europe it was first recorded in 1984 from Southern Italy (SANNINO *et al.* 1984, 1985, 1986). Subsequently it has been reported from France (MOUTTET *et al.* 2017), Portugal (ISRAELSON 1985), Spain (VIÑOLAS *et al.* 2016, PETITPIERRE *et al.* 2017), Albania (KRSTESKA & STOJANOSKI 2012), Greece (LYKOURESSIS 1991), Hungary (LUKÁTSI *et al.* 2022), North Macedonia (KRSTESKA & STOJANOSKI 2012), Russia (ORLOVA-BIENKOWSKAJA 2014), Slovenia (SELJAK 2017), Turkey (DÖBERL 1994a), and Bulgaria (TRENČEV & TOMOV 2000). First records for both Romania and Serbia are presented here.

Host plants – It is a well-known pest of several cultivated species of Solanaceae, especially tobacco (*Nicotiana* spp.). In Hungary, Romania, and Serbia it has been recently observed feeding on *Datura stramonium*, a wild species of Solanaceae. Though wild solanaceans such as *Datura stramonium* and *Physalis pubescens* L. (Solanaceae) have already been reported as host plants of this species in Europe (GOURVES & SAMUELSON 1979, ISRAELSON 1985, KRSTESKA & STOJANOSKI 2012, BIEŃKOWSKI & ORLOVA-BIENKOWSKAJA 2016, EDDE 2022), up to now, within Hungary, the species has been found exclusively in or near tobacco plantations.

Longitarsus albineus (Foudras, 1860)

Material examined – **Hungary:** Csongrád-Csanád County, Szeged, Kisteleki út, maize stubble-field, 46.2964°N, 20.0810°E, from *Heliotropium europaeum* L. (Boraginaceae), 22.IX.2024, leg. M. Lukátsi & V. A. Nagy, det. M. Lukátsi (1 male! CLM); Jász-Nagykun-Szolnok County, Szajol, Alamand-dűlő, 47.1661°N, 20.2672°E, from *Heliotropium europaeum*, 1.IX.2024, leg. & det. M. Lukátsi (4 CLM, 3 (incl. 1 male!) HNHM). **Serbia:** Voivodina Region, Stari Žednik, stubble-field, 46.0003°N, 19.6491°E, from *Heliotropium europaeum*, 22.IX.2024, leg. M. Lukátsi & V. A. Nagy, det. M. Lukátsi (1 male! HNHM).

Distribution – A Western Palaearctic species known from Afghanistan, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Croatia (incl. Adriatic Islands), Cyprus, France (incl. Corsica), Greece (incl. Ionian Islands and Rhodos), Hungary, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Italy (incl. Sardinia and Sicily), Jordan, North Macedonia, Portugal, Romania, Serbia (first country record, presented here), Slovakia, Spain (incl. Balears), Tajikistan, Turkey, Ukraine, and Uzbekistan in Europe and the Middle East; and from Algeria, Egypt, Morocco, and Tunisia in Africa (GRUEV & DÖBERL 1997, 2005).

Host plants – Recorded food plants of *Longitarsus albineus* include *Heliotropium bovei* Boiss., *Heliotropium europaeum*, *Heliotropium hirsutissimum* L., *Heliotropium maris-mortui* Zohary, *Heliotropium supinum* L. (all Boraginaceae), and *Helianthemum* spp. (Cistaceae) (FOUDRAS 1860, BARGAGLI 1878, PORTA 1934, MÜLLER 1953, FURTH 1980, JOLIVET 1967, WARCHAŁOWSKI 1978, BIONDI 1990a, b, DOGUET 1994, WARCHAŁOWSKI 1995, BIONDI 1996, WARCHAŁOWSKI 1996, ČIŽEK 2006, ČIŽEK & DOGUET 2008), of which *Heliotropium europaeum* can be found in agricultural fields after the crops have been harvested.

Longitarsus aphthonoides Weise, 1887

Material examined – **Hungary:** Zala County, Kerkabarabás, marsh meadow, swept, 13.VI.2021, leg. M. Lukátsi & K. Bakardzsiev, det. L. Farina (1 female! CLM, 1 female! CFL).

Distribution – A Eurasian species known from Austria, Azerbaijan, China (Heilongjiang, Fujian), Czechia, France, Germany, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, North Korea, Poland, Russia (Republic of Dagestan; Khabarovsk, Krasnoyarsk, and Primorsky Krai; Amur, Irkutsk, and Sakhalin Oblast), Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland, and Turkey; in North Africa from Tunisia (FARINA 2021). In Hungary it is considered a rare species, prior to this study it has only been recorded from two localities in the western part of the country (Győr-Moson-Sopron County: Csáfordjánosfa (VIG 2002a), and Zala County: Zalaegerszeg (POZSGAI 2005)).

Host plants – *Longitarsus aphthonoides* was observed on *Sanguisorba officinalis* L. (Rosaceae), *Lythrum salicaria* L. (Lythraceae), *Onobrychis viciifolia* Scopoli (Fabaceae) (WARCHAŁOWSKI 1996, RHEINHEIMER & HASSLER 2018, ÖZDIKMEN *et al.* 2020). It is not clear whether these plants are its actual host plants because other species of its species group live on *Stachys* and *Teucrium* spp. (Lamiaceae) (FARINA 2021).

Longitarsus brisouti Heikertinger, 1912

Material examined – **Hungary:** Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County, Bököny, Szárhegy tanya, reed, swept, 5.VI.2022, leg. N. Tóth, det. L. Farina (1 male! CLM); same but 9.IV.2024, det. M. Lukátsi (1 female! CLM); 3 km NW of Bököny, Bökönyi-folyás, reed, swept, 31.III.2023, leg. N. Tóth, det. L. Farina (1 female! CLM); same but 9.V.2024, det. M. Lukátsi (1 male! HNHM).

Distribution – The species is known in Europe from Belgium, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, France (incl. Corsica), Germany, Greece (incl. Ionian Islands), Hungary, Italy (incl. Sardinia and Sicily), Montenegro, Romania, Russia (Republic of Adygea, Volgograd Oblast), Slovakia, Slovenia, and Spain; in Asia from Turkey (GRUEV & DÖBERL 1997, 2005). It is considered a rare species in Hungary, with less than ten occurrence records from the country (TOMOV *et al.* 1996).

Host plants – *Cupularia viscosa* (L.) G. G., *Inula britannica* L., *Jacobaea erucifolia* (L.) G. Gartn., B. Mey et Scherb, *Senecio gallicus* Chaix, *Senecio vulgaris* L. (all Asteraceae); *Scrophularia* spp. (Scrophulariaceae) (BIONDI 1990a, GRUEV 1992, DOGUET 1994, BIONDI & DI CASOLI 1996, BIONDI & DE NARDIS 2001, BRELIH *et al.* 2003, ČIŽEK 2006, ČIŽEK & DOGUET 2008, RHEINHEIMER & HASSLER 2018).

Longitarsus cizeki Döberl, 2004

Material examined – **Hungary:** Pest County, 2 km E of Apaj, former fish ponds, swept, 28.VI.2020, leg. M. Lukátsi, det. L. Farina (1 female! CLM, 2 males! CFL); Pest County, Érd, SÁNC-hegy, loess steppe, swept, 4.VIII.2018, leg. M. Lukátsi, det. L. Farina (1 female! CLM); Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County, Bököny, Szárhegy tanya, reed, swept, 3.VI.2022, leg. N. Tóth, det. L. Farina (1 male! HNHM); same but 15.VI.2022 (1 male! CLM).

Distribution – The species is known in Europe from Germany, Hungary, and Slovakia (RHEINHEIMER & HASSLER 2018).

Host plants – *Jacobaea erucifolia* (L.) G. Gartn., B. Mey et Scherb (Asteraceae) (DÖBERL 2004, ČIŽEK 2006, ČIŽEK & DOGUET 2008, RHEINHEIMER & HASSLER 2018).

Remarks – This species was described by DÖBERL (2004) from Slovakia based on specimens previously identified as *Longitarsus jacobaeae* (Waterhouse, 1858). It was reported from Germany based on old specimens by RHEINHEIMER & HASSLER (2018) and from Hungary by FRITZLAR (2021) (Baranya County, Drávasztára, 1996, leg. M. Eifler). *Longitarsus cizeki* closely resembles *Longitarsus jacobaeae* and *Longitarsus flavicornis* (Stephens, 1831); from those it can be distinguished mainly by the shape of the aedeagus. The first protarsomere of the male of *Longitarsus cizeki* is also narrower than that of *Longitarsus jacobaeae* (DÖBERL 2004).

Longitarsus fulgens (Foudras, 1860)

Material examined – **Hungary:** Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County, Bököny, Szárhegy tanya, sand steppe pasture, sifted, 10.II.2021, leg. N. Tóth, det. L. Farina (1 male! CLM); same but reed, swept, 30.V.2021, leg. N. Tóth, det. M. Lukátsi (1 CFL).

Distribution – The species is known in Eurasia from Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Czechia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia (Belgorod Oblast, Republic of Dagestan, Krasnoyarsk Krai), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, and Ukraine (GRUEV & DÖBERL 1997, 2005). In Hungary it was found near Kis-Balaton and Mosonmagyaróvár in 1950 (KASZAB 1962) and in the Bakony Mountains in 1979 (ROZNER 1990). The new record confirms its occurrence in Hungary after 42 years.

Host plants – *Lycopus europaeus* L., *Mentha arvensis* L., *Scutellaria galericulata* L. (all Lamiaceae) (BOURDONNÉ 1992, DOGUET 1994, BIONDI 1996, LEONARDI & SASSI 1997, ČIŽEK 2006, BRENNER 2007, ČIŽEK & DOGUET 2008, RHEINHEIMER & HASSLER 2018).

Longitarsus kutscherae (Rye, 1872)

Material examined – **Hungary**: Baranya County, 6 km N of Pécs, Tripammerfa, swept, 24.VI.2017, leg. M. Lukátsi et al., det. L. Farina (1 male! CLM).

Distribution – The species is known in Eurasia from Albania, Austria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Belarus, Bulgaria, China (Inner Mongolia), Czechia, Denmark, England (incl. Scotland), Finland, France (incl. Corsica), Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, North Korea, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Belgorod and Omsk Oblast), Slovakia, Slovenia, South Korea, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and Turkey; in Africa from Algeria (GRUEV & DÖBERL 1997, 2005). It is very rare in Hungary, known only from a few locations on the plains and from the hills of Őrség, Aggtelek (VIG 2002a), and Mecsek (present study).

Host plants – *Plantago lanceolata* L., *Plantago major* L. (Plantaginaceae); *Galeopsis speciosa* P. Mill., *Galeopsis tetrahit* L., *Lamiaeum galeobdolon* (L.) Ehrend et Polatschek (Lamiaceae); *Melampyrum nemorosum* L., *Melampyrum sylvaticum* L. (Orobanchaceae); *Myosotis arvensis* Hill (Boraginaceae); *Cirsium oleraceum* L. (Asteraceae) (WARCHAŁOWSKI 1970, 1978, FOGATO & LEONARDI 1980, BIONDI 1990a, DÖBERL 1994b, DOGUET 1994, WARCHAŁOWSKI 1995, 1996, BIONDI 1996, BRELIH *et al.* 2003, WARCHAŁOWSKI 2003, ČIŽEK 2006, ČIŽEK & DOGUET 2008, WARCHAŁOWSKI 2010, RHEINHEIMER & HASSLER 2018).

Longitarsus longiseta Weise, 1889

Material examined – **Hungary**: Nógrád County, 1 km SW of Garáb, Garábi-patak, swept, 21.IV.2018, leg. M. Lukátsi et al., det. L. Farina (1 CLM); Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County, Bököny, Szárhegy tanya, swept, 15.VI.2024, leg. N. Tóth, det. M. Lukátsi (1 male! CLM); Pest County, Szokolya, Tax-rét, swept, 6.VI.2020, leg. M. Lukátsi, det. L. Farina (1 CFL).

Distribution – The species is known in Europe from Austria, Bulgaria, Belarus, Czechia, England, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia (Republic of Dagestan and Karelia), Slovakia, Slovenia, and Switzerland; in Asia from China (Heilongjiang), Japan, North Korea, and Russia (Primorsky Krai) (GRUEV & DÖBERL 1997, 2005). It is rare in Hungary (VIG 2002b).

Host plants – *Plantago lanceolata* L. (Plantaginaceae), *Veronica officinalis* L., *Veronicastrum sibirica* (L.) Pennell (Scrophulariaceae) (KRÁL 1954, MOHR 1962, 1966, WARCHAŁOWSKI 1970, 1978, FOGATO & LEONARDI 1980, BIONDI 1990a, DÖBERL 1994b, DOGUET 1994, WARCHAŁOWSKI 1995, 1996, BIONDI 1996, LEONARDI & SASSI 1997, BRELIH *et al.* 2003, ČIŽEK 2006, SASSI 2007, ČIŽEK & DOGUET 2008, RHEINHEIMER & HASSLER 2018).

Longitarsus minusculus (Foudras, 1860)

Material examined – **Hungary:** Pest County, Ócsa, Dabasi úti rét, wet meadow, swept, 1.V.2020, leg. M. Lukátsi, det. L. Farina (1 male! CLM); Baranya County, Nagyarsány, Szársomlyó, rocky grassland, swept, 23.VI.2017, leg. M. Lukátsi et al., det L. Farina (2 (incl. 1 male!) CLM).

Distribution – The species is known in Europe from Austria, Belgium, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia (incl. Adriatic Islands), Czechia, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy (incl. Sardinia), Montenegro, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Republic of Dagestan), Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain (incl. Balears), Switzerland, and Ukraine; in Asia from Turkey (GRUEV & DÖBERL 1997, 2005). It is rare in Hungary, known only from the vicinity of Budapest, and from some locations in Transdanubia and Aggtelek Hills (VIG 1999).

Host plants – *Ballota nigra* L., *Betonica officinalis* (L.) Trev., *Phlomis glandulifera* Klokov, *Prasium majus* L., *Salvia sylvestris* L., *Sideritis hyssopifolia* L., *Sideritis romana* L., *Stachys ocymastrum* (L.) Briq., *Stachys recta* L., *Teucrium chamaedrys* L., *Teucrium palium capitatum* (L.) Arcangeli, *Teucrium scorodonia* L. (all Lamiaceae); *Turritis glabra* L. (Brassicaceae) (WEISE 1893, HEIKERTINGER 1912, 1926, PORTA 1934, KRÁL 1945, MÜLLER 1953, MOHR 1962, WARCHAŁOWSKI 1969, 1978, BIONDI 1990a, BOURDONNÉ 1992, GRUEV 1992, DÖBERL 1994b, DOGUET 1994, WARCHAŁOWSKI 1996, LEONARDI & SASSI 1997, BRELIH *et al.* 2003, ČIŽEK 2006, SASSI 2007, ČIŽEK & DOGUET 2008, RHEINHEIMER & HASSLER 2018).

Longitarsus nanus (Foudras, 1860)

Material examined – **Hungary:** Budapest, Tétényi-fennsík, swept, 1.VIII.2022, leg. M. Lukátsi, det. L. Farina (1 male! and 1 female! CLM, 1 HNHM, 1 CFL); Pest County, Perócsény, Hangyás-bérc, swept, 6.VI.2022, leg. M. Lukátsi, det. L. Farina (1 CFL).

Distribution – The species is known in Eurasia from Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, France, Germany, Greece (incl. Ionian Islands and Rhodos), Hungary, Israel, Italy (incl. Sardinia), Latvia, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Poland, Russia (Republic of Dagestan), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain (incl. Balears), Switzerland, Turkey, and Ukraine; in Africa from Algeria (GRUEV & DÖBERL 1997, 2005). The second and third records from Hungary are presented here, the only reliable earlier record is from the Aggtelek Hills from 1997 (VIG 1999).

Host plants – *Marrubium cuneatum* Banks et Sol., *Prunella grandiflora* (L.) Scholler, *Sideritis hyssopifolia guillonii* (Timb.) Rouy, *Stachys recta* L., *Teucrium bracteatum* Desf., *Teucrium chamaedrys* L., *Teucrium montanum* L., *Teucrium polium* L., *Teucrium scorodonia* L. (all Lamiaceae) (DE PEYERIMHOFF

1915, HEIKERTINGER 1926, MÜLLER 1953, MOHR 1962, 1966, JOLIVET 1967, FURTH 1980, BIONDI 1990^a, GRUEV 1992, WARCHAŁOWSKI 1978, DÖBERL 1994^b, DOGUET 1994, WARCHAŁOWSKI 1995, 1996, BIONDI 1996, BIONDI & LAURENZI 1997, BRELIH *et al.* 2003, ČIŽEK 2006, ČIŽEK & DOGUET 2008, RHEINHEIMER & HASSLER 2018).

Longitarsus personatus Weise, 1893

Material examined – **Hungary:** Nógrád County, 1 km SW of Garáb, Garábi-patak, swept, 21.IV.2018, leg. M. Lukátsi *et al.*, det. L. Farina (1 CLM).

Distribution – The species is widely distributed in the eastern Euro-Mediterranean area. It occurs in Europe (Austria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, France, Germany, Greece (incl. Crete and Rhodos), Hungary, Italy, Moldova, Montenegro, Romania, Russia (Krasnodar Krai), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland, and Ukraine; in Asia (Cyprus, Israel, and Turkey) (FARINA 2021). In Hungary it was reported from the Mecsek, Vértes, and Buda Hills and some locations on the Great Hungarian Plains (Bátorliget, Monor, and Sarkad) (FARINA 2021).

Host plants – Because *Longitarsus personatus* and *Longitarsus lateripunctatus* (Rosenhauer, 1856) were only recently distinguished as separate species (FARINA 2021), older host plant records are now ambiguous and require critical reassessment. However, both species are associated with members of Boraginaceae: *Anchusa azurea* Miller, *Borago longifolia* Poiret, *Borago officinalis* L., *Cerintho major* L., *Cynoglossum creticum* Mill., *Pulmonaria mollis* Wolff., *Pulmonaria obscura* Dumort, *Pulmonaria officinalis* L., *Symphytum officinalis* L., *Symphytum palestinum* Boiss., *Symphytum tuberosum* L. (HEIKERTINGER 1926, MÜLLER 1953, FURTH 1980, DOGUET 1994, KIPPENBERG 1994, WARCHAŁOWSKI 1996, BRELIH *et al.* 2003, ČIŽEK 2006, RHEINHEIMER & HASSLER 2018). The second author observed *Longitarsus lateripunctatus* on *Echium plantagineum* L. and *Echium tuberculatum* Hoffmanns et Link (Boraginaceae) in collection trips to Puglia (Castro, March 2024) and Portugal (Aljezur, Praya do Odeceixe, December 2024), respectively. *Pulmonaria officinalis* is here confirmed as host plant for *Longitarsus personatus* based on specimens recently collected from this plant species in Czechia (Znojmo, April 2025) by the second author.

Longitarsus salviae Gruev, 1975

Material examined – **Hungary:** Budapest, Tétényi-fennsík, swept, 1.VIII.2022, leg. M. Lukátsi, det. L. Farina (1 male! CLM); Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County, Bököny, Szárhegy tanya, reed, swept, 14.VI.2022, leg. N. Tóth, det. M. Lukátsi (1 male CFL).

Distribution – The species is known in Eurasia from Armenia, Austria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, France, Georgia, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, North Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Russia (Krasnodar Krai), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, and Ukraine (Crimea only) (GRUEV & DÖBERL 1997, 2005). In Hungary it has been known from Hortobágy, Tihany, and the Bükk National Park (ROZNER 1990, TOMOV *et al.* 1996); the present study reports it from Budapest and Nyírség (Bököny).

Host plants – *Salvia nemorosa* L., *Salvia pratensis* L., *Salvia verticillata* L. (Lamiaceae) (BIONDI 1983, 1990a, DÖBERL 1994b, DOGUET 1994, WARCHAŁOWSKI 1995, 1996, BIONDI 1996, LEONARDI & SASSI 1997, BRELIH *et al.* 2003, ČIŽEK 2006, SASSI 2007, ČIŽEK & DOGUET 2008, RHEINHEIMER & HASSLER 2018).

Longitarsus strigicollis Wollaston, 1864

Material examined – **Hungary:** Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County, Bököny, Közös-legelő, under *Dipsacus* sp. (Caprifoliaceae) leaves, 10.III.2023, leg. N. Tóth, det. L. Farina (1 male! CLM); Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County, Bököny, Közös-legelő, under *Dipsacus* sp. leaves, 9.III.2023, leg. N. Tóth, det. L. Farina (1 female! CFL); Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County, Bököny, Szárhegy tanya, swept, 28.VI.2022, leg. N. Tóth, det. L. Farina (1 female! CLM); Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County, Bököny, Szárhegy tanya, at light, 4.VII.2022, leg. N. Tóth, det. L. Farina (1 CFL).

Distribution – This species is known in Eurasia from Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Italy (incl. Sardinia and Sicily), Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain (incl. Balears), Switzerland, and Turkey; in Africa from Algeria, Morocco, Tunisia, and in the Atlantic Islands from the Canary Islands (La Gomera, La Palma, Tenerife), and Cape Verde Islands (GRUEV & DÖBERL 1997, 2005). In Hungary it has been reported from the Kiskunság, the hills of Aggtelek and Bakony (VIG 1999, 2002b), and Nyírség (present study).

Host plants – *Dipsacus fullonum* L., *Dipsacus laciniatus* L., *Dipsacus sativus* L., *Pycnocomon rutifolium* (Vahl.) Hoffmanns. et Link, *Scabiosa atropurpurea* (L.) Greuter et Burdet, *Scabiosa columbaria* L. (all Caprifoliaceae) (DOGUET 1994, BIONDI 1996, ČIŽEK 2006, ČIŽEK & DOGUET 2008, RHEINHEIMER & HASSLER 2018). BIONDI (1990a) and BIONDI & LAURENZI (1997) mentioned unspecified members of Lamiaceae.

Longitarsus tristis Weise, 1888

Material examined – **Hungary**: Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County, 3 km NW of Bököny, Bökönyi-folyás, reed, swept, 31.III.2023, leg. N. Tóth, det. M. Lukátsi (1 male! CLM); Szabolcs-Szatmár-Bereg County, Bököny, Szárhegy tanya, swept from *Quercus* sp. (Fagaceae), 24.V.2024, leg. N. Tóth, det. M. Lukátsi (1 male! CLM); Hajdú-Bihar County, Téglás, train station, swept, 14.V.2024, leg. N. Tóth, det. M. Lukátsi (1 male! CLM).

Distribution – The species is known in Europe from Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, Germany, Hungary, Romania, Russia (Republic of Dagestan, Orenburg Oblast), Slovakia, and Ukraine (GRUEV & DÖBERL 1997, 2005). In Hungary it occurs sporadically (VIG & ROZNER 1996).

Host plants – Its food plants are *Scutellaria hastifolia* L. and *Stachys palustris* L. (both Lamiaceae) (DÖBERL 1994b, WARCHAŁOWSKI 1996, ČIŽEK 2006, ČIŽEK & DOGUET 2008, RHEINHEIMER & HASSLER 2018).

*

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